

The Influence of Card Sort Learning Media on Students' Learning Outcomes in Subtheme 1 How Clean Air Processes by Body in Grade V UPTD SDN 122337 Pematang Siantar

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ARTICLEINFO

Keywords: Learning Media, Card Sort, Learning Results

Received : 6, September

Revised : 10, October

Accepted: 18, November

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine whether there is an influence of Card Sort Learning Media on student learning outcomes in theme 2, subtheme 1, how the body processes clean air. In class V UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar, the method in this research is a quantitative experimental type method whose research design is Pre -experimental type one group pretest-posttest. Conducted in October 2023, the population was all students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar and the sample used was a saturated sample of 30 students. The variant used is two research variables: dependent variable (x) Card Sort learning media (y) student learning outcomes, data collection techniques, namely test techniques with validity tests, reliability tests, difficulty level tests, and distinguishing power tests. The test results using the Normality test, Homogeneity test and the N-gain technique with the help of the SPSS version 21 program, based on the calculation results, the homogeneity test was obtained using the Levene's test of 0.097, i.e. greater than 0.05. The pre-test nil results which have an average of 46.33 while the average post-test nil results are 82.83 compared to the final nil results or the difference between pre-test and post-test nil results is 36%. Judging from its level of significance, it can be classified into the significant category. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the use of the Card Sort learning model on students' learning outcomes in class 2 sub-story 1 class V at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the bases for efforts to develop and increase student potential by encouraging and providing various facilities for the teaching and learning process. Education is also an area that is of great concern to every direction, especially Indonesia which has the potential to greatly increase education. Based on Law number 20 of 2003 article 1 (1), it explains that education is a place or forum that develops all human potential in order to create and have religious spiritual strength, intelligence, personal personality and the skills needed in himself, his family and society. as well as the nation.

Learning activities must be carried out in order to create a good learning process too. To achieve success, one way is to look at student learning outcomes. Which is an aspect that will be considered in planning a lesson from learning activities. In Boom's taxonomy concept, aspects of learning outcomes are divided into 3 domains, namely:

- 1) cognitive domain
- 2) affective domain
- 3) psychomotor domain (Magdalena, et al: 2020).
- 4) Thus, the learning outcomes are in the form of students' abilities that they receive after receiving the subjects. From there the teacher can find out to what extent the students have understood the learning.

Based on observations made at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar in class V in May. The observation results obtained still show low learning outcomes with data on daily test scores for Indonesian language subjects, 41% of students have completed and 59% of students have not completed science subjects, 45% of students have completed and 55% of students have not completed them. Where there are still many students who have no interest in learning and students who are inactive, indifferent, and even like to chat with their classmates. They think that Indonesian and science lessons are boring, which results in many students feeling sleepy and bored during the lesson. In fact, there are no students who want to answer the questions given by the teacher after the learning process is complete. So this kind of implementation results in students having difficulty understanding the content of the material being presented as well as low student learning outcomes, where if the learning outcomes are low it will result in the learning process carried out at school not being carried out well.

As well as the solutions used to deal with these problems, as teachers must create a good and effective learning atmosphere, teachers must also be able to create a conducive learning environment or a classroom atmosphere that is pleasant, comfortable and clean. So that students are interested and can follow the learning well. By using Card Sort learning media.

The learning media that researchers apply is Card Sort learning media, where this learning media can help students to increase students' understanding of learning material and the learning material is more easily conveyed to students. Card Sort learning media is a learning media in the form of pieces of paper containing paper about the material that will be taught to students. The advantages of this Card Sort media are:

- 1) make it easier for students to receive lesson material
- 2) students are more enthusiastic and enthusiastic in learning
- 3) implementation is easy and simple
- 4) increase students' interest in learning The weaknesses in this Card Sort learning media are :
 - a. Students are less active in speaking and giving opinions
 - b. Students who don't understand will have difficulty adjusting to their groups
 - c. If the teacher is not careful, it can take up time in providing learning material.

Especially in learning to maintain human respiratory organs so that it can teach students to know about maintaining human respiratory organs, and students create ideas or questions that can make them active in the learning process. That is why teachers must be wise in providing learning media that attracts students' attention so that the teacher's hopes and aspirations can be realized.

Based on the background above, the researcher is very interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence of Card Sort Learning Media on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Sub-theme 1 How the Body Processes Clean Air in Class V UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual framework can be prepared influence Card Sort Learning Media on Student Learning Outcomes in Class V in Theme 2 Subtheme 1 How the Body Processes Clean Air at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar .

In observations made by researchers at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar, the resulting learning process tends to be teacher-centered, students are less active in the learning process and students tend to be passive due to being sleepy and daydreaming and learning seems boring and does not attract students' attention during the process. learning.

So teachers need media that can improve the learning outcomes of class V students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar. Learning Media n Card Sort is a learning media that can be used to attract students' attention in understanding the lesson that will be delivered. The aim of creating Card Sort learning media is to change student learning outcomes that were previously low or high to become optimal and higher in the learning process.

METHOD

The research used in this research uses a quantitative approach. According to Sugiyono (2021), quantitative research methods are research methods that are based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, collecting data using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of examining predetermined hypotheses. This research uses a Pre-Experimental Design type of research using The One Group Pretest-Posttest Design.

According to Sugiyono (2021) an experiment is a research method carried out by experiment, which is a quantitative method, used to determine the independent variable (treatment) against the dependent variable (outcome) under controlled conditions.

In research, the results of the treatment will be known more accurately because the situation can be compared before the treatment was given. The following is a picture of One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design, Sugiyono (2021)

O1 X O2

Figure 3.1 One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design

Location:

O1 = before treatment is given

X = when given treatment

O2 = after treatment

The population in this study were all students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar with a total of 30 students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Test instrument

1. Test validity

Of the 30 questions after the instrument test at school, there were 20 valid questions and 10 invalid questions. So what is distributed are questions with a total of 20 valid statements. Because the questions distributed are questions that meet several criteria which are assisted by the use of the Microsoft Excel 2010 application.

2. Reliability Test

The rehabilitation test aims to see the accuracy of the tool in assessing what it assesses. In this case, observe how each question item is determined in assessing or testing students' abilities and knowledge.

Reliability Results Table

Reliability	$\sum pq$	6.09
	Score Variance	37.62
	Kr20	39.12

(Source: Microsoft Elxcell 2010)

Based on the results of the reliability test with the Kr20 model above, we can see that the value is high. Then it can be concluded that the data is declared reliable.

3. Difficulty Level Test

That the easy question category is 10 questions (2,3,5,7,8,11,12,14,27,29), currently available question categories 19 question (1,4,6,9,10,13,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,28) and the difficult question category contains 1 question (20) .

4. Differentiating Power Test

Category contains 8 questions (1,4,6,10,16,18,21,23), sufficient category 11 questions (2,7,8,9,13,14,24,25,26,28,29), bad category 9 questions (3,5,11,15,17,19,22,27,30) and bad category once 2(12,20).

Data analysis

This research was carried out at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar in class V with 30 students as research samples. In this research, the scores from two variables consist of 20 questions in the form of multiple choices which were given to 30 students as research samples. These two variables are student learning outcomes

before treatment (Pre-Test) and learning outcomes after treatment using Card Sort media learning (Post-Test).

1. Normality Test

The Normality Test is used to see whether the data obtained comes from a population with a normal or abnormal distribution. This normality test uses the SPSS program with the Komogorov-Smirnov program with Lilielfors correction criteria. The basis for decision making in this test is:

Table 4.7 Test of Normality

Kolmogorov-smilrnova			Shopilro-Willk		
statilstilc	DF	Silg	Statilstilc	DF	Silg
,162	30	,044	,964	30	,391
,165	30	,037	,929	30	,046

(Source: SPSS processing version 21)

2. Homogeneity Test

This test is used for find out whether the data is homogeneous or not. This homogeneity test uses ILBM SPSS version 24 with the following results.

Table 4.12 Test of Homogeneity of Fariances

Levelvelnel statilstilc	Df 1	Df 2	Silg
.2848	1	58	,097

(source: SPSS processing version 21)

3. N-Gain Test

This test is used to see the percent increase in student learning outcomes and the class average

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Milnilmum	Maxilimum	Melan	Std. delvilstilon
N_Gainscore	30	.40	1.00	7657	.16093
N_Gainpercent	30	40.00	100.00	76.5685	16.09263
Valid N (listwise)	30				

(source: SPSS Processing version 21)

The table above shows that the Melan N-Gain score and N-Gain percent are 0.76, which is included in the high category.

Discussion

Of Card Sort Teaching Media on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Subtheme 1 How the Body Processes Clean Air in Class V UPTD SDN 122337 Pematang Siantar . In this research, researchers used an experimental type of research using a One Group Pretest-Posttest Design research design. Before using Learning Media in the teaching and learning process, it is an effort to increase the effectiveness and quality of the learning process which can ultimately improve student learning outcomes. In this study, researchers used Card Sort Learning Media as learning media. However There are still difficulties in using this media, namely the ability required in the manufacturing process to make it more interesting, creative and innovative, so teachers must be able to apply Card Sort Learning Media. The ease of using this media is that the material is presented with certain points, making it easier for teachers to convey and explain the material to students. Based on existing theory, it is suspected that the learning outcomes of students who are taught using Card Sort Learning Media are better than students who are taught without using it. Card Sort Learning Media. Judging from the hypothesis testing data, it turns out that the assumption is correct. With the rejection of H_0 and supported by data obtained during the research, namely a comparison of study statistical scores showing that there were 30 people in the sample, with the lowest pretest score being 20 and the highest being 100. The lowest posttest score was 75, while the highest posttest score was 100, with an average The pretest score is 46 and the average is 82. In other words, learning using Card Sort Learning Media is better than learning without using Card Sort Learning Media. This is possible because of the different approaches when using media and when not using media. Using media can motivate students to be active, make the teaching and learning process more enjoyable and increase student motivation to seek information about subjects which can improve student learning outcomes in learning. Meanwhile, without using media, more students listen to the teacher's lecture so they are less effective in learning. The influence of Card Sort learning media on student learning outcomes, namely student learning outcomes where student learning outcomes have increased.

This researcher means that the hypothesis in this research is accepted, namely that there is an influence of Card Sort Learning Media on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Sub-theme 1 How the Body Processes Clean Air in Class V UPTD SDN 122337 Pematang Siantar. The results of this research are in accordance with previous research conducted by Yenti Juniarti et al (2022) which shows that there is an influence of Card Sort Learning Media on learning outcomes. So it can be stated that there is an influence of Card Sort Learning Media on student learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

In accordance with the results of research conducted by researchers, researchers can conclude that there is an influence of Card Sort learning media on student learning outcomes in theme 2 sub-theme 1 How the Body Processes Clean Air in class V at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar. This is proven by the results of validity tests carried out on the influence of Realia media. From the results of the normality test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov, the significant value of the pretest results was 0.44. While the posttest was 0.37. So it can be concluded that the experimental class obtained significant results >0.05 so that the normality test was distributed normal.

In the homogeneity test using Levene's test, a significant value of 0.097 was obtained, which is greater than the table of 0.05. Likewise, the pretest score results have an average of 46.33, while the posttest results have an average value of 82.83, the comparison value or increase from pretest to posttest score is 36 %. Meanwhile, the N-Gain test results have a mean value of 0.76. If seen from the level of significance, it can be classified into the effective category. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the use of Card Sort learning media on student learning outcomes in theme 2 subtheme 1 class V at UPTD SD Negeri 12237 Pematang Siantar.

Recommendation

Based on the results of research that has been carried out with the title the influence of Card Sort learning media on student learning outcomes in theme 2 sub-theme 1 how the body processes clean air in class V UPTD SDN 122337 Pematang Siantar, the following suggestions can be given:

1. Suggestions for Teachers

It is best that in the teaching and learning process teachers apply Card Sort learning media so that students can collaborate with their friends and not feel bored during learning. Teachers give students the freedom to find problems and how to solve them in learning so that learning is not only teacher-centered but student-centered.

2. Suggestions for Researchers

This research can be a basis for developing one's potential and finding out about many interesting learning media so that researchers can apply new media in the future when they enter the field.

3. Suggestions for Schools

It is hoped that schools can support this Card Sort learning media to be implemented in schools to develop knowledge among students, because this Card Sort media can make students' curiosity higher and they can see directly examples in the learning process.

4. Suggestions for Students

To all students at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar to be more enthusiastic about learning and train themselves to adapt to each learning media applied by the teacher in order to create a new, interesting and comfortable learning atmosphere.

EFERENCES

- Andriyanto, S. S., ed. Pembelajaran dan media pembelajaran. Penerbit Lakeisha, 2023.
- Arikunto, Suharsimi. Dasar-dasar evaluasi pendidikan edisi 3. Bumi Aksara, 2021.
- Bahri, Saiful. Pengaruh Penerapan Pendekatan Contextual Teaching and Learning Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Kelas IV Tema Daerah Tempat Tinggalku di Sdn Summersari 01 Jember. Diss. 2019.
- Dimiyati, Mudjiono. "Belajar dan pembelajaran." Jakarta: Rineka Cipta (2006).
- Gaol, Bintang Kasih Lumban, Patri Janson Silaban, and Anton Sitepu. "Pengaruh Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Pada Tema Lingkungan Sahabat Kita Di Kelas V SD." Jurnal PAJAR (Pendidikan dan Pengajaran) 6.3 (2022): 767-782.
- Halidi, Hasan Mahmud, Sarjan N. Husain, and Sahrul Saehana. "Pengaruh media pembelajaran berbasis TIK terhadap motivasi dan hasil belajar IPA siswa kelas V SDN Model Terpadu Madani Palu." Mitra Sains 3.1 (2015): 53-60.
- Hamalik, Oemar. "Proses belajar mengajar." (2006)..
- Hidayah, Nurul, Riska Wahyuni, and Anton Tri Hasnanto. "Pengembangan media pembelajaran gambar berseri berbasis pop-up book untuk meningkatkan keterampilan menulis narasi bahasa indonesia." Terampil: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran Dasar 7.1 (2020): 59- 66.
- Islam, Mochamad Rahmatulloh Syaeful. "Efektivitas Pembelajaran Mata Pelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam melalui Metode Make A Match dalam Mengenal Malaikat dan Tugasnya." Prosiding Pendidikan Agama Islam (2017): 140-146

Juniarti, Yenti, Ketut Minda, and Setiyo Utoyo. "Pengaruh Media Pembelajaran Card Sort Terhadap Kemampuan Literasi Membaca Anak." *Jurnal Pelita PAUD* 7.1 (2022): 1-6.

Likunusa, Enriko, Juliana M. Sumilat, and Mayske R. Liando. "Pengaruh Penggunaan Media Pembelajaran Video Pada Pembelajaran Tematik Tema 4 Kelas 2 Sd Negeri 2 Tomohon." *Edu Primary Journal* 3.2 (2022): 65-78.

Nafiati, Dewi Amaliah. "Revisi taksonomi Bloom: Kognitif, afektif, dan psikomotorik." *Humanika, Kajian Ilmiah Mata Kuliah Umum* 21.2 (2021): 151-172.

Ningsih, Putri Rahayu. *Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Pop Up Book Pada Pembelajaran Tematik Kelas IV SD/MI*. Diss. UIN Raden Intan Lampung, 2020.

Novita, Lina, Elly Sukmanasa, and Mahesa Yudistira Pratama. "Penggunaan media pembelajaran video terhadap hasil belajar siswa SD." *Indonesian Journal of Primary Education* Penggunaan 3.2 (2019): 64-72.

Nurrita, Teni. "Pengembangan media pembelajaran untuk meningkatkan hasil belajar siswa." *Jurnal Misykat* 3.1 (2018): 171-187.

Pramudya, Erviyanti, Firosalia Kristin, and Indri Anugraheni. "Peningkatan keaktifan dan hasil belajar ipa pada pembelajaran tematik menggunakan pbl." *Naturalistic: Jurnal Kajian dan Penelitian Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran* 3.2 (2019): 320-329.

Pratiwi, Inesa Tri Mahardika, and Rini Intansari Meilani. "Peran media pembelajaran dalam meningkatkan prestasi belajar siswa." *Jurnal Pendidikan Manajemen Perkantoran* 3.2 (2018): 173-181.

Rahma, Fatikh Inayahtur. "Media Pembelajaran (kajian terhadap langkah-langkah pemilihan media dan implementasinya dalam pembelajaran bagi anak Sekolah Dasar)." *Pancawahana: Jurnal Studi Islam* 14.2 (2019): 87-99.

Rapii, Muhammad, and Muh Fahrurrozi. "Evaluasi Hasil Belajar." (2017): 1-171.

Rokhimawan, Mohamad Agung, And Nur Leli. "Pengaruh Strategi Point Counter Point Terhadap Keterampilan Berbicara Dalam Pembelajaran Tematik." *TERAMPIL: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran Dasar* 5.2 (2018): 247-257

Safa, Icha Mutiara. Kemampuan Menghafal Ayat Al-Qur'an Dengan Menggunakan Metode Card Sort Dalam Pembelajaran Agama Islam di Sekolah Menengah Pertama Negeri 1 Rogojampi. Diss. Fakultas Tarbiyah Dan Ilmu Keguruan Program Studi Pendidikan Agama Islam, 2021.

Safitri, Merna. "Pengaruh Strategi Pembelajaran Aktif Tipe Card Sort Terhadap Hasil Belajar IPS Siswa Kelas IV SD Negeri 10 Metro Timur." (2017).

Sepwanda, Monica, and Damai Yani. "Persepsi Siswa Terhadap Card Sort Sebagai Media Pembelajaran Hiragana." *Omiyage: Jurnal Bahasa Dan Pembelajaran Bahasa Jepang* 4.1 (2021): 42-50.

Sugiyono, Sugiyono, and Puji Lestari. "Metode penelitian komunikasi (Kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan cara mudah menulis artikel pada jurnal internasional)." (2021).

Supriyono, Supriyono. "Pentingnya Media Pembelajaran Untuk Meningkatkan Minat Belajar Siswa Sd." *Edustream: Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar* 2.1 (2018): 43-48

Yulianti, Hesti, Cecep Darul Iwan, and Saeful Millah. "Penerapan Metode Giving Question And Getting Answer Untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Peserta Didik Pada Mata Pelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam." *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Islam*,[SL] 6.2 (2018): 197-216.